

THE TRAGEDY OF THE ARAL SEA AND WAYS TO MITIGATE ITS
CONSEQUENCES.

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Annotation: *The drying up of the Aral Sea in the early 1960s. Once the oral was One of the cleanest seas in the world, because of the policy of the USSR on growing cotton, the oral ceased to receive water from the Amu Darya and Syr Darya. In the end, the Aral became the biggest environmental disaster of the 20th century. Now the problem of drying up the Aral has a global character. Dust and salt flying out of the dried-up part of the Aral Sea spreads to the whole world. To solve this problem, scientists around the world are developing various projects.*

Keywords: *anthropogenic-natural ecological catastrophe. reservoirs, evaporation, sea level, climate, groundwater.*

The decrease in the level of the Aral Sea is an anthropogenic-natural ecological catastrophe associated with the loss of 90% of the water volume of the Aral Sea in the second half of the 20th century and the formation of the Aralkum desert in its place. According to the calculations of modern scientists, the influence of anthropogenic factors on the decline in the level of the Aral Sea exceeded 70%. A sharp decline began in connection with the development of agriculture in the Aral Sea region, in the first place - the intensive cultivation of cotton in irrigated fields. To irrigate plantations by the 1960s, the entire flow of the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers feeding the Aral Sea was dismantled, numerous reservoirs and canals arranged upset the balance between water inflow and evaporation. In 1985-1986, the sea level dropped from 53 to 41 m (relative to the level of the Baltic Sea), the Berg Strait dried up, the Aral broke up into two independent reservoirs - the Big and the Small. By 2002, the level dropped by another 10m, in 2006, the deep-water part, the former Tshe-Bas Bay, separated from the Big Aral. From 1960 to 2009, the area of the Aral Sea has decreased from 67499 km² to 6700 km².

According to the World Meteorological Association, the drying up of the Aral Sea is one of the largest anthropogenic environmental crises of the 20th century. Within a radius of up to 100 km from the former borders of the sea, the climate changed to sharply continental, the amount of precipitation decreased several times, tugai forests perished, more than 130 species of animals and 30 species of fish disappeared. Dust storms carry over long distances the sand from the dry bottom and the chemical pollutants accumulated in it. Dust transport provoked a multiple increase in respiratory, eye, oncological and other diseases among the population of the Aral Sea region.

The degradation of the Aral Sea began in the 1950s in connection with the new economic strategy of the Soviet Union: the country needed cotton for light industry, the production of ammunition and rocket fuel. The ideal region for its cultivation was Central Asia. Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan and southern Kazakhstan, which were part of the USSR, became its "cotton granary". Plantations were irrigated using water from the basins of the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers, the main sources of water for the Aral Sea. In the period until the 1960s, the water flow was compensated by the return flow from the collector-drainage networks, but since the 1960s this balance has been sharply disturbed.

Collector-drainage waters flowing from the fields into the Syr Darya and Amu Darya channels have caused deposits of pesticides and other agricultural pesticides, appearing in places on 54 thousand km² of the former seabed covered with salt. Dust storms carry salt, dust and pesticides to a distance of up to 500 km. Sodium bicarbonate, sodium chloride and sodium sulfate are airborne and destroy or slow down the development of natural vegetation and crops.

In 2001, as a result of a drop in the water level, Vozrozhdeniye Island was connected to the mainland. Until 1992, a Soviet military biochemical laboratory operated on this island, which tested bacteriological weapons - anthrax, tularemia, brucellosis, plague, typhoid, smallpox, as well as botulinum toxin - on laboratory animals.

During the period from 1960 to 2016, the total area of the Aral Sea (including the modern Big and Small Aral) decreased nine times, the total volume decreased 21 times.

As of 2019, the Aral Sea was divided into five periodically communicating reservoirs: the Big Aral, which broke up in 2001 into the eastern and western parts, the Small Sea, the Tshe-Bas Bay and the Central Aral. The western basin of the Great Sea is fed by groundwater, which slows down drying, but in general the water balance remains negative and salinity continues to increase. It is connected to the eastern part by the Uzun-Aral Strait.

The Central Aral is a shallow, vast lake overgrown with reeds. In the western part, it has a salinity of about 70 g/l. The regime of the lake is unstable and varies greatly depending on the season and the total water content of each year. In winter and spring, the increased flow of the Syr Darya reaches it from the Small through the Big Aral, in the summer-autumn period the Central Aral can completely dry up[50][51].

Is it possible to save the Aral Sea?

Under the condition of a complete cessation of water intake from the drains of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya, it would take more than 100 years to restore the previous sea level. Five countries in the basin—Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan—with the support of the European Union and other countries, are implementing projects to partially restore the Aral Sea. Modern scientists consider the revival of the Aral Sea impossible.

The Big Aral is going through hard times: it continues to shrink rapidly. The shallow pool in the east and the deeper western pool are now connected only by a long narrow channel, and there is no certainty that one day it will not completely dry up. According to scientists, if the countries through which the Amu Darya flows do not change anything, then the isolated eastern reservoir, at the current rate of groundwater inflow and evaporation, can stabilize on an area of 4300 km². At the same time, its average depth would be 2.5 m, and the salinity of the water would exceed 100 g/l, possibly even reaching 200 g/l. The only inhabitants of such an environment would be brine shrimp and bacteria.

The fate of the western reservoir depends on the inflow of groundwater. The scientist Aladin (head of the laboratory of brackish waters at the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, RF) noticed numerous freshwater springs on the western coastal ledges. According to calculations, this reservoir should retain an area of

about 2100 sq. km. It will remain relatively deep, reaching a depth of 37m in places, but its water salinity will be well over 100g/l.

Large-scale construction of a number of hydraulic structures could contribute to the restoration of the western reservoir. One old plan for the restoration of the entire Aral Sea, which was recently adjusted by a professor of geography at Western Michigan University Miklin, will also come in handy. Since this project has not been carefully evaluated, the cost of its implementation is unknown, but it can be a significant amount. It provides for a fairly modest increase in the flow of the Amu Darya through rational improvements to the irrigation system in the river's catchment area. An important element of the plan is also the restoration of local reed floodplains.

A fish factory in the city of Aralsk also started working, contributing to the growth of the local economy. Image: "In the world of science"

Similar work began in the late 1980s. in the Soviet Union, continued today by Uzbekistan. At present, we can already talk about minimal success in restoring the biological diversity of water bodies, fishing and natural filtration of wastewater with the help of aquatic vegetation (primarily reeds), but there is no quick solution to the problem. The drying up of the Aral Sea continued for more than 40 years. Long-term, sustainable solutions will require not only major capital investment and technical innovation, but also fundamental political, social and economic transformations.

Mexico experience

— In the nineties and early 2000s, there were big programs to reduce water consumption from the World Bank. The experience of Israel and Mexico was taken as a basis, where much less water is used for irrigation.

But these technologies were not implemented in the end, most likely due to their high cost and the complexity of these systems. And people are not interested in saving water, because it is free.

In this regard, for now, everything remains the same. Now there is a slight decrease in water consumption, but not so large as to mitigate the ecological situation.

- But will the introduction of complex irrigation systems - like, for example, in Israel, help to increase the flow of water into the Aral Sea?

- Undoubtedly. The experience of Mexico, a developing country, where there are not as many resources as in Israel, will be even more useful here.

Mexico managed to reduce water consumption by half compared to the Central Asian countries thanks to well-thought-out engineering systems. In addition, we set strict water quotas, began to comply with irrigation technology, and use modern equipment to control costs. That is, the state began to tightly control the consumption of water, and farmers began to use water sparingly, and the state supports them in this in various ways.

One of the biggest environmental disasters of the 20th century has been partly reversed, according to a report claiming that the water levels in the Aral Sea are rising again.

The team behind the Aral Sea Restoration Plan claims water levels in the northern part of the sea in Central Asia have risen by 30% in three years because a dam has been built

and leaking irrigation canals have been repaired. As a result, the amount of water flowing down the Syr Darya to the sea has increased.

Now the salty, drying waters, which have dwindled to contain only one species of fish, are now home to 15 different species of fish and more birds, reptiles and plants, the Kazakh government said in a report.

Fishing has also been rejuvenated, and the second phase of a program to restore pastures and improve grazing is currently underway.

"The return of the northern Aral Sea shows that man-made disasters can be at least partially reversed, and that food production depends on the sound management of scarce water resources and the environment," said World Bank President Robert Zoellick in his report, a statement issued through the government.

As the water level dropped from a depth of 53 m to 30 m and receded 100 km from the coast, the salt concentration killed most of the remaining wildlife.

"While the current levels of various species have not yet reached pre-50s levels, they are improving every year," the spokeswoman said.

However, the scheme preserves only a very small part of what was once the world's fourth largest sea - the new surface area is less than half of the entire sea in 1960, and although studies of some of the remains of the southern part have concluded that some areas cannot be saved.

Ongoing efforts to save the Aral Sea

"Serving as the EU climate bank, the European Investment Bank (EIB) has recently joined the international effort to save the Aral Sea, building on the Bank's years of experience in assessing and financing environmental projects in more than 150 countries. . Today, the EIB is working on a comprehensive package of measures aimed at mitigating the negative effects of decades of inadequate irrigation and enabling Uzbekistan to gradually regain control over the environment and economy of the Aral Sea Basin," the Bank is considering a €100 million investment plan to address the main sources of environmental catastrophe and works closely with partners in Uzbekistan to ensure maximum effectiveness of rescue operations in the Aral Sea.

The program is also aligned with European institutions, including the European Commission, the European External Action Service and the EU Delegation to Uzbekistan. Dialogue is ongoing with other international financial institutions, such as the World Bank, to further expand partnerships and develop truly sustainable action for the people, environment, and economy of Uzbekistan, Central Asia, and the world.

This activity supports the government of Uzbekistan and its efforts to save the Aral Sea from extinction. In 2017, the government launched an initiative to create a United Nations Multilateral Trust Fund for the Development of the Aral Sea Region and is currently working on planting about two million hectares of new plantations and forests, as well as demanding the return of land from the desert.

Solving major problems

The EU Bank is looking for ways to help modernize and upgrade the current resource-inefficient irrigation and drainage infrastructure and achieve significant water savings

targets of 20 to 25%. This should reduce the level of water withdrawal from the Amu Darya and increase the flow of water into the Aral Sea.

“We are also exploring how to help restore the productivity of degraded and abandoned land and create agroforestry sites for biodrainage. The result will not only be savings in water use, but also increased carbon sequestration through biodrainage of degraded lands. We also want any future project to contribute to the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goal No. 15 and the UNCCD targets on land neutrality (LDN),” explained V.P. Pavlova.

The operation should also create the conditions for sustainable and environmentally sound agriculture, which could justify similar climate action and conservation efforts in the Amu Darya basin in the coming years.

It could also lead to a long-term, constructive partnership between the EU and Uzbekistan, beneficial both for the EU and Uzbekistan, and for the whole world. “Saving the Aral Sea requires an all hands on deck approach from the international community, both in terms of support and resources. If successful, this would allow us to correct a terrible mistake and leave a better world for our children,” concluded Lilyana Pavlova.

In the conditions of the southern Central Asian deserts, saxaul pasture protection belts noticeably increase relative humidity, change the temperature regime of air and soil, reduce wind speed, retain snow and protect the soil from drying out. As a result, more favorable hydrothermal conditions are created for the growth and development of natural wormwood-ephemeral vegetation in the strip itself and in adjacent pasture areas.

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